

Developing Kameshwar Mahadev Temple into a Regional Tourist Destination: Planning, Infrastructure, and Promotion Strategies

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Abstract- Religious tourism is one of the most important and significant sectors of the Indian tourism industry. It plays a major role in contributing to economic growth, employment generation, infrastructure development, cultural preservation, and regional development. Gujarat is the one of the states from India which has rich religious heritage and some of them are known worldwide such as Somnath, Dwarka, Ambaji, Dakor and Palitana. However, some other religious destinations are underdevelopment though they have tourism potential. One such destination is Kameshwar Mahadev Temple, situated on the bank of the Ambika River in Gadat village, Navsari District, Gujarat. The main purpose of this research is to investigate the potential for sustainable development of Kameshwar Mahadev Temple as a regional religious tourism destination. The study evaluates the temple's historical significance, geographical setting, tourism resources, visitor characteristics, existing infrastructure, environmental attributes, and socio-economic context. Furthermore, it examines opportunities and constraints associated with tourism development through SWOT analysis and sustainable tourism assessment frameworks. The research uses the mixed-method approach which is based on secondary data, demographic analysis, tourism statistics, infrastructure assessment, policy review, and qualitative evaluation. Findings indicate that Kameshwar Mahadev Temple possesses significant strengths including religious importance, strategic accessibility, natural landscapes, cultural heritage, and an established visitor base. Nevertheless, deficiencies in tourism infrastructure, accommodation facilities, sanitation, destination marketing, and community participation continue to constrain its development potential. This study introduces a master plan for tourism that combines better roads and facilities, environmental protection, community involvement, smart marketing, and teamwork among local authorities. The findings show that focusing on sustainable tourism can turn the Kameshwar Mahadev Temple into a major regional pilgrimage site. This development will boost the local economy and create jobs for residents while fully protecting the surrounding natural resources.

Keywords- Religious Tourism, Sustainable Tourism Development, Rural Tourism, Temple Tourism, Pilgrimage, Gujarat Tourism, Community-Based Tourism, Kameshwar Mahadev Temple.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is a social, cultural and economic phenomenon related to the movement of people to places outside their usual place of residence. From this understanding and the fact that tourism is a temporary activity, it can be interpreted that tourism is a demand-based concept. The decision of the tourist to make a visit generates additional demand for goods and services, which are provided from the supply side either through increased domestic production or through imports.

Tourism is a collection of activities, services and industries that delivers a travel experience, including transportation accommodations, eating and drinking establishments, retail shops, entertainment business, activity facilities and other hospitality services provided for individuals or groups travelling away from home.

According to UNWTO "Tourism refers to the activity of visitors. A visitor is a traveller taking a trip to a main destination outside his/her usual environment for less than a year, for any main purpose (business, leisure or other personal

purpose) other than to be employed by a resident entity in the country or place visited.”

Numbers of International Tourists as per UNWTO data are:

Year	Number of Tourists
1950	25 mil
1980	275 mil
1995	528 mil
2012	1035 mil
2014	1133 mil

Table 1.1 Numbers of International Tourists In addition, there are 5 to 6 billion domestic tourists.

A. Forms of Tourism

Tourism has two types and many forms on the bases of the purpose of visit and alternative forms of tourism. Tourism can be categorized as international and domestic tourism.

Tourism has various forms on the basis of purpose of visit and alternative forms. These are further divided into many types according to their nature. Forms of tourism are following as:

Figure 1.1 Types and Forms of Tourism

Some most important forms of tourism are following as:

Adventure Tourism, Beach Tourism, Cultural Tourism, Ecotourism, Industrial Tourism, Medical Tourism, Religious, Tourism, Rural Tourism, Sex Tourism, Space Tourism, Sports Tourism, Sustainable Tourism, War Tourism, Wildlife Tourism

B. Importance of Tourism

Tourism and hospitality, which are inextricably linked to each other, are among the major revenue-earning enterprises in the

world. They happen to be among the top employers too. There has been an upmarket trend in tourism over the last few decades as travel has become quite common. People travel for business, vacation, pleasure, adventure or even medical treatments. With several business-related activities associated with tourism, the industry has a tremendous potential of generating employment as well as earning foreign exchange. There are many countries in the world, such as Mauritius, Malaysia, Singapore, Fiji, and the Caribbean, whose economies are primarily driven by tourism.

Tourism can contribute to the economic growth of a country in the following ways:

- Employment Generation
- Infrastructure Development
- Foreign Exchange

C. Impacts of Tourism

Establishing or developing a tourism industry involves expenditure as well as gains, costs, and benefits. If these impacts are taken into consideration from the outset of planning, strengths and opportunities can be maximized while weaknesses and threats can be minimized.

Each destination will be different in terms of tourism characteristics. The cost and benefits of tourism will vary in each destination and can change over time, depending on tourism and other activities in a destination’s local and regional context.

Economic Impacts: Tourism activities impact the economy of the country as well as the local economy of the destination

a. Economics Benefits

- Tourism generates local employment, directly in the tourism sector and in support and resource management sectors.
- Tourism stimulates profitable domestic industries, hotels and other lodging facilities, restaurants and food services, transportation systems, handicrafts, and guide services.
- Tourism generates foreign exchange for the country and injects capital and new money into the local economy.
- Tourism helps to diversify the local micro economy.
- Improved tourism infrastructure.
- Increase tax revenues from tourism.

b. Economic Costs

- Higher demand created by tourism activity may increase the price of land, housing and a range of commodities necessary for daily life.
- Demands on health services provision and police service increase during the tourist seasons at the expense of the local tax base.

Social Impacts : Tourism also affects the society of the destination in good as well as bad ways. It benefits and costs the local communities.

c. Social Benefits

- The quality of a community can be enhanced by economic diversification through tourism.
- Recreational and cultural facilities created for tourism can be used by local communities as well as domestic/international visitors.
- Public spaced may be developed and enhanced through tourism activity.
- Tourism Enhances local community's esteem and provides an opportunity for greater understanding and communication among people of diverse background.

d. Social Costs

- Rapid tourism growth can result in the inability of local amenities and institutions to meet service demands.
- Without proper planning and management, litter, vandalism, and crime often accompany tourism development.
- Tourism can bring overcrowding and traffic congestion.
- Visitors bring with them material wealth and apparent freedom. The youths of the host community are particularly susceptible to the economic expectations these tourists bring and can result in complete disruption of traditional community ways of life.
- The community structure may change, e.g. community bonds, demographics, and institutions.
- The authenticity of the social and cultural environment can be changed to meet tourism demands.

Cultural Impacts : Tourism activities also affect the culture of the host country. There are many positive and negative cultural impact of tourism.

a. Cultural Benefits

- Tourism can enhance local cultural awareness.
- Tourism can generate revenue to help pay for the preservation of archaeological sites, historic buildings, and districts.
- Despite criticism about the alteration of cultures to unacceptable levels, the sharing of cultural knowledge and experience can be beneficial for hosts and guests of tourism destinations and can result in the revival of local traditions and crafts.

b. Cultural Costs

- Youth in the community begin to emulate the speech and attire of tourists.
- Historic sites can be damaged through tourism development and pressures.
- There can be long-term damage to cultural traditions and the erosion of cultural values, resulting in cultural change beyond a level acceptable to the host destination.

Environmental Impact : Tourism impacts on the environment in positive as well as negative way. These impacts are following below.

c. Environmental Benefits

- Parks and nature preserves may be created and ecological preservation supported as a necessity for nature-based tourism.
- Improved waste management can be achieved.
- Increased awareness and concern for the environment can result from nature-based tourism activities and development.

d. Environmental Costs

- A negative change in the physical integrity of the area.
- Rapid development, over-development, and overcrowding can forever change the physical environment and ecosystems of an area.
- Degradation of parks and preserves.

D. Tourism in India

Compared to many countries, India has the advantages of possessing a rich and diverse range of unique tangible and intangible cultural, natural and man-made tourism resources, many of which are world class in quality. India's great competitive strength from tourism point of view is its ancient and yet living civilization that gave rise to four of the world's

great religions and philosophies, and brought travelers and trade millennia ago. The rich natural and rural landscape of India is punctuated with the built heritage of its ancient past and modern structures. India's contacts with other civilizations is reflected in the rich cultural diversity of its people through its languages, cuisine, traditions, customs, music, dance, religions practices and festivals, its holistic healing traditions, art and craft.

According to the latest data compiled by the Ministry of Tourism, number of international tourist arrivals in India was 6.58 million in 2012, posting an annual growth of 4.3 per cent, higher than the world growth. Domestic tourism, which accounts for a bulk of tourism in India, grew by 19.9 per cent with total domestic tourists visiting all states and UTs of India numbered at 1036 million. India's foreign exchange earnings from tourism stood at US\$ 17.74 billion in 2012, growing by 7.1 per cent. This places India at 41st rank in terms of its share in world tourist arrivals and at 16th position in terms of its share in world tourism receipts.

With respect to the contribution of tourism to the GDP of India, the second Tourism Satellite Account of 2009-10 estimates it at 3.7 per cent as the direct share and 6.8 per cent, taking indirect impact also into account. This brings tourism to one of the top sectors of Indian economy in terms of contribution to economy. Tourism sector contributes significantly to the creation of jobs as well. It is estimated to have created 23.4 million jobs in 2009-10, which translated to a share of 4.4 per cent in the total employment. This sector also contributed 54.5 million jobs indirectly, which increased its share to 10.2 per cent.

Within the non-agriculture employment, tourism had a share of 9.7 per cent in employment and if indirect share is included, the share goes up to 22.6 per cent. This implies that almost every 4th to 5th person employed in non-agricultural activities is directly or indirectly engaged in tourism activities. An exercise to update these numbers on annual basis till the release of third Tourism Satellite Account reveals that the share of tourism in GDP moderated to 3.6 per cent in 2010-11 due to the overall slowdown in general economy but recuperated in the following year and contributed 3.7 per cent to GDP in 2011-12. Accordingly, the total (direct and indirect) share fell from 6.77 per cent in 2009-10 to 6.68 per cent in 2010-11 but upped at 6.74 per cent in 2011-12.

The share of Tourism industries' employment in total employment grew from 4.4 per cent in 2009-10 (according to Second TSA) to 4.6 per cent in 2010-11 and to 4.9 per cent in 2011-12. Its direct and indirect share escalated from 10.2 per cent in 2009-10 to 10.8 per cent in 2010-11 and settled at 11.5 per cent in 2011-12.

E. Tourism in Gujarat

Gujarat is one of the major tourism-oriented states of India. In terms of number of domestic tourist arrival in 2010, the state ranks at the tenth place and the rank in terms of foreign tourist arrival is 15. Eight major tourism hubs have been developed in Gujarat namely Ahmedabad Metro, Ahmedabad Rural, Surat, Vadodara, Rajkot, Junagarh & Jamnagar (Saurashtra) and Bhuj (Kutch).

Gujarat is well known place for pilgrimage places. Swaminarayan and Akshardham temples in Ahmedabad, Dwarkadhish and ISKON temples in Dwarka, Somnath Temple in Saurashtra,

Shankheshwar Jain temples and Girnar Hill temple are some of the most famous and religiously followed places located in Gujarat. All these places attract high number of pilgrims to Gujarat. Gujarat, especially Ahmedabad and nearby region including the state capital Gandhinagar is a major hub of internationally renowned educational institutions which attract education tourists of higher education from each corner of the country. These prestigious institutes include Indian Institute of Management and National Institute of Design in Ahmedabad, National Institute of Fashion Technology and Indian Institute of Technology in Gandhinagar and Institute of Rural Management in Anand. All these institutions including the famous Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) located in Ahmedabad attract many tourists travelling with purposes of attending meetings & seminars and education & training.

Gujarat is renowned for its beaches, historic architectural assets, wildlife sanctuaries and hill resorts which are major attraction for leisure tourists.

According to the data compiled by the India Tourism Statistics, the total domestic tourist arrivals in the state rose from 82.7 lakh in 2001 to 2.74 crore in 2010, marking the compounded annual growth rate of 10.5 per cent.

During the same period, foreign tourist arrival grew by five times, from 30,930 to 1,98,773 with the compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 16.8 per cent.

Table 1.2 Purpose of Tourist Flow

Purpose	2004-05 Flow		2005-06 Flow		2006-07 Flow	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Business	4.06	94	5.67	55	6.53	53
Leisure	0.39	5	0.51	5	0.96	8
Religion	2.81	37	3.84	38	4.33	35
Other	0.34	4	0.48	4	0.53	4
Total	7.61	100	10.70	100	12.34	100

F. Religious Tourism

For Hindus, Gujarat has important sites like two jyotirlingas at Somnath and Dwarka (Nageshwar), one of the four dhams at Dwarka, two of the 51 shakti peeths at Ambaji (Legend says heart fell) and Mahakali in Pawagadh; one of the five holy lakes of India at Narayan Sarovar; and one of the seven holiest rivers of the Hindus is the Narmada which flows through Gujarat. There are also important temples at Dakor, Virpur, Khodiyar, Sarangpur, etc. The Bhuvaneshwari temple of Gondal is among the two in India. These temples attract Hindus from around India and many Hindu NRIs visit these holy places at least once in their lifetime. Three of the four most important pilgrimages for the Parsees – Sacred Iranshaw Fire Temple at Udvada, Navsari Atashbehram and Surat Atashbehram – are in Gujarat. Besides these,

Sanjan, where the Parsees landed in India is also in Gujarat. Akshardham, Gadhada, Bachosan, Gondal, Sarangpur, etc. are some of the famous Swaminarayan temple. Swaminarayans form a wealthy sect. Two of the five important Jain sites in India are at Palitana and Girnar. In addition to these, there is a regular flow of Jain pilgrims to Sankeshwar, Taranga, Kumbhariyaji, Badhreshwar, Mandvi 79 Jinalaya, Naliya, Mahudi, etc. The dargahs of Sarkhej and Unjha are among the much-visited Islamic sites of India. The ashrams of Morari Bapu, Rameshji Oza, etc are on the spiritual tourism map of India.

Figure 1.2 Somnath Temple

II. INTRODUCTION TO SITE

Kameshwar Mahadev is an ancient temple under a Banyan tree on the bank of the ambika river in gadat. Devotees from Navsari and surat severally visit this temple. Kameshwar Mahadev temple is also known for Shiv sarovar. During sravan month highest number of tourists visit this temple. Local people also organize several havan and yagna at this place. This place is only recognized in regional level this place is not nationally recognized.

A. Geographic Location

Kameshwar Mahadev is an ancient loacted in Gujrat state, navsari district on the bank of the ambika river in gadat village, which is 17km. Far from navsari. This temple is located between Manekpur.

a). Surrounding Area :

According to Census 2011 information the location code or village code of Gadat village is 522998. Gadat village is located in Gandevi Tehsil of Navsari district in Gujarat, India. It is situated 3km away from sub-district headquarter Gandevi and 15km away from district headquarter Navsari. As per 2009 stats, Gadat village is also a gram panchayat. The total geographical a rea of village is 317.98 hectares. Gadat has a total population of 2,129 peoples. There are about 479 houses in Gadat village. Gandevi is nearest town to Gadat which is approximately 3km away.

Figure 3 geographic Location

b). Connectivity of Gadat

Public Bus Service Available within village
 Private Bus Service Available within <5 km distance
 Railway Station Available within 10+ km distance

Table 3 Gadat Village Overview

Gadat - Village Overview	
Gram Panchayat :	Gadat
Block / Tehsil :	Gandevi
District :	Navsari
State :	Gujarat
Pincode :	396350
Area :	317.98 hectares
Population :	2,129
Households :	479
Nearest Town :	Gandevi (3 km)

B. History

It is believed that this place is the end of aahwa-dang forest and the Ashram of the saint Garg used to be on this place is important to the temple of kameshwar mahadev nine planets have been carved on one stone. This place is important to the temple of planets in kasha. It is believed that the person who sits under this banyan tree become free from disease. Lotuses blossom In the lakes next to the temple. There are two elephants of stone decorating the entrance of the temple. This temple is five thousand years old. Just now this temple has been renovated.

C. Demographics data

Gadat Village:

Gadat is a large village located in Gandevi Taluka of Navsari district, Gujarat with total 479 families residing. The Gadat village has population of 2129 of which 1063 are males while 1066 are females as per Population Census 2011. In Gadat village population of children with age 0-6 is 168 which makes up 7.89 % of total population of village. Average Sex Ratio of Gadat village is 1003 which is higher than Gujarat state average of 919. Child Sex Ratio for the Gadat as per census is 750, lower than Gujarat average of 890.

Table 4 demographic data of gadat village

Particulars	Total	Male	Female
Total No. of Houses	479	-	-
Population	2,129	1,063	1,066
Child (0-6)	168	96	72
Schedule Caste	18	6	12
Schedule Tribe	719	362	357
Literacy	95.46 %	96.79 %	94.16 %
Total Workers	833	675	158
Main Worker	618	-	-
Marginal Worker	215	139	76

Manekpor :

Manekpor is a large village located in Chikhli Taluka of Navsari district, Gujarat with total 573 families residing. The Manekpor village has population of 2518 of which 1261 are males while 1257 are females as per Population Census 2011. In Manekpor village population of children with age 0-6 is 287 which makes up 11.40 % of total population of village. Average Sex Ratio of Manekpor village is 997 which is higher than Gujarat state average of 919. Child Sex Ratio for the Manekpor as per census is 1095, higher than Gujarat average of 890.

Table 5 demographic data of manekpor village

Particulars	Total	Male	Female
Total No. of Houses	573	-	-
Population	2,518	1,261	1,257
Child (0-6)	287	137	150
Schedule Caste	35	19	16
Schedule Tribe	1,271	642	629
Literacy	86.69 %	90.66 %	82.66 %
Total Workers	943	691	252
Main Worker	854	-	-
Marginal Worker	89	25	64

III. AIM OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To attract the MICE segment, by creating convention/exhibition facility and support infrastructure

- To leverage innovative forms of tourism such as adventure, cruise, event-based, inland waterways, medical and others
- To develop diverse tourism packages and products to augment tourist stay and encourage repeat visits;
- To promote tourism for all segments of the society especially facilitating senior citizens, the differently-abled, homemakers, farmers and students, by ensuring affordable accommodation and travel circuits;
- To provide tourism infrastructure in terms of tourist information, transport services, accommodation and way-side amenities;
- To enhance the use of ICT in the sector and further improve the quality of services
- To promote responsible tourism in the State and develop tourism products in an environment-friendly manner.
- To create enabling framework for public-private partnerships in developing tourism products, projects and services.

IV. TEMPLE LOCATION AND MAP

Figure 4 view of Kameshwar Mahadev templ

Figure 5 Road map for gadatgam to Kameshwar Mahadev temple

Figure 6 Plan of Kameshwar Mahadev templ

A. Development & Facilities

Figure 7 available land parcel, current development & facilities available

- Zinnodhar of Kameshwar Temple along with Navagraha with beautiful parisar.
- Satsang Bhavan with eleven rooms that includes furniture and other amenities for stay.

- Kameshwar alphahar gruh for the refreshment
- Mini train for kids entertainment.
- Balkrindaghan for kids that features swings, slides, and other activities.
- Huge parking next to temple on block No.405
- Grah, Nakshatra and Rashivatika with plants accordingly.
- The beautiful island in the Shiv Sarovar where magnificent statue is going to take place.
- Pleasant pathway leading to the Kameshwar Sankul between the Shiv Sarovar with bridge joining the two parts of Shiv Sarovar.
- Good amount of donation to purchase the land along with Kameshwar Sankul Ca.82,000 Sf. Etc etc...
- Shiv Sarovar: We are planning the beautiful statue of Lord Shiva in “Dhyanastha Mudra”. Statue “Lord Shiva” will be 72 feet heigh. “Dwadarsh Jyotirlingas” along with “Shiv Parivar”, “Dharmik Library & Museum” and the beautiful garden on the island.
- The Boating activities in Shiv Sarovar, which will start soon for recreation of visitors.

Figure 4-5 View of Kameshwar Mahadev mandir

B. Nearby attraction circuit

There are Andheshwar Mahadev Temple and also Manekpur Haat attraction places in this region for tourism.

Figure 4-6 Nearby attraction of Kameshwar Mahadev

Andheshwar Mahadev :

The ancient Andheshwar Mahadev Temple at Amalsad in Ganadevi is a great center of faith for devotees and a large number of Shiva devotees take advantage of darshan here. The history of Swayambhu Shivling of Andheshwar Mahadev Temple is 900 years old. According to the Ambika Purana, Lord Shiva defeated the powerful demon Andhak by climbing the tip of his trishul and later included him in his gana. According to the legend, the lingam is called the god of Andhak i.e. Andakeshwar or Andheshwar. According to folklore, a blind Banjara cow living in the jungles of Amalsad used to milk the self-styled Shivling in the bushes. When Banjara got information about this, she worshiped Shivalinga with reverence. During this time a miracle happened and he got the eye light.

After this incident, Shivling is famous as Andheshwar. Vanzara later built a pagoda of 84 pillars here. In 1400 AD, the Desai of Ganadevi got the temple renovated. Later the temple was rebuilt in the Peshwa and Chalukya periods. The existing facilities adjacent to the lake include a temple that is visited by over 200,000 people every week. In addition, a learning centre, library, community hall, food stalls, gardens & dormitories form the extensive campus area.

Figure 4-7 plan of Andheshwar Mahadev temple

Figure 4-8 View of Andheshwar Mahadev temple

Manekpur Haat :

Manekpur is a small village panchayat located in Gandevi Taluka in Navsari District of Gujarat State, India. It comes under Gram Panchayat. It is located 14 KM towards South from District head quarters Navsari. 9 KM North from Taluka place Gandevi. 309 KM from State capital Gandhinagar. Manekpur Pin code is 396350 and postal head office is Gadat (Navsari). Manekpur is surrounded by Navsari Taluka towards North , Jalalpure Taluka towards west , Mahuva Taluka towards East , Chikhali Taluka towards South. A haat bazaar, most often called simply haat, is an open-air market that serves as a trading venue for local people in of Manekpur.

Haat bazaars are conducted on a regular basis by mostly local inhabitants. Usually haat caters to the daily need of neighborhood populace, as well as provides selling platform for local produces. Manekpore haat is being held every Sunday morning on panchayat ground. Residents of nearly 20+ villages rely on this haat for their house supplies, clothing, groceries etc. Haat also serves as place for entertainment for kids and social interaction for neighboring villages. Haat also act as a revenue source for Manekpore Gram Panchayat.

Figure 9 views of Manekpore haat

C. Tourist data for Kameshwar, Andeshwar & Haat

Nos of tourist month wise

Table 6 Nos of tourist month wise

Month	Kameshwar Mahdev Temple	Kameshwar Mahdev Temple	Manekpur Haat
JAN	936	1783	376
FEB	906	2793	412
MAR	1067	3780	750

APR	1145	3456	50
MAY	1356	4789	453
JUN	974	3566	354
JUL	845	2477	217
AUG	1869	3655	211
SEP	1031	5670	764
OCT	976	2358	198
NOV	847	3777	398
DEC	798	2349	367

Mode of Travel

- Visitors By Car 20%
- Visitors By Two Wheeler 38%
- Visitors By State Transportation 42%
- NH 8 Navsari - Gadat Stopage at Kameshwar temple.
- Valsad -Gadat - Extension from Gadat to Kameshwar temple
- Public Infrastructure like Primary School in Gadat , Aanganwadi, Sahakari mandali can be used for devotees accommodation.

Figure 10 Tourist data for Kameshwar, Andeshwar & Haat

Figure 11 Tourist come for visit from neighboring town or city

V. ROLE OF AUTHORITY

Governments have a critical role to play in development of rural tourism especially during the initial stages. Governments can provide infrastructure, pro rural tourism policy, capacity building, incentives, information and training, networking, promotion and distribution. Government can play the role of promoter, mediator, facilitator and regulator. The rural development policies are often not integrated with different policies of the area. Each department of the Government goes about development in its own way. Most of the times, there is lack of communication between these departments. The rural tourism development policies need to be integrated with environment, transport, economic, agricultural and land use policies to make all round development of the area. Sometimes there is no political will to give priority to rural development. Sometimes there is political will as well as policy in place but it is an ineffective execution due to lack of implementation mechanism.

A. State Government Involvement

Consideration of Guidelines for Development.

- **Identification of villages:** Each State/UT Govt, would be requested to furnish one proposal for promotion of rural tourism. Based on the merits and after a joint inspection by the Department of Tourism and the State/UT Government, if required ten proposals would be identified for implementation in the country. Preparation of detailed plan for implementation of the project: After short-listing
- The proposals, the State/UT Governments would be requested to draw up a detailed plan of action.
- The thrust here would be to achieve convergence between the different schemes of the Govt, of India and the State Governments. It should be ensured that at least 50% of the project should be implemented through achieving convergence of different schemes. Assistance up to INR 3 lakhs would be provided to the State Govt, for engaging an expert for preparing the project report.

Permission activities: The following works under the Scheme

- Improvement of the surroundings of the village. This would include activities like landscaping, development of parks, fencing, compound wall etc.

- Improvements to roads within the Panchayat limits. This shall not include any major road which connects the village,
- Illumination in the village,
- Providing for improvement in solid waste management and sewerage management. Construction of Wayside Amenities,
- Procurement of equipment's directly related to tourism, like Water Sports, Adventure Sports, Eco-friendly modes of transport for moving within the selected zone,
- Refurbishment of the Monuments, Sign ages, Reception, Parking.
- Tourist Accommodation (Existing Public Infrastructure like Schools can be used as dormitories for devotees.

YDVB (Yatra Dham Vikas Board)- Shraavan Tirthdarshan Yojana

The state government has launched the Shraavan Tirthdarshan Yojana in 2017 under the scheme, the government will pay 50% costs of tirth yatra by non-AC state transport bus, within the state, for groups of senior citizens, regardless of the communities to which they belong. The scheme is exclusively meant for senior citizens to help them cover important religious destinations in Gujarat.

Under this initiative, groups of senior citizens will have to make travel plans of two night and three-day programmes and approach respective state transport depots. The representative of the YDVB (Yatra Dham Vikas Board) will certify the same and the 50% of the journey cost by non-AC ST bus will be borne by the state.

VI. PREVAILING ISSUES

A. Deprivation, Improper Communication Facilities

Rural markets are often characterized by rural population and majority of them still come under below Poverty Line. These villagers are less involved in showcasing their culture and heritages in front of the tourists visiting their places as they are not very much aware of the potentiality of rural tourism that can act as an alternative source of earning and therefore there will be lesser need to go to nearby town in search of job. Moreover, most of the rural markets are underdeveloped with lots of hindrances. Long distance from nearby towns, absence of proper mode of surface transportation, lack of basic infrastructure, inadequate lodging-boarding, amusement

facilities, inconsistent electricity, telecommunication problem etc. cause difficulties to attract valued consumers (tourists) in many rural sites though those are very much promising in term of the availability of tourism resources.

Lack of Co-operation and understanding among governing local bodies and their leaders regarding development of the site.

B. Communication Skill

There is no doubt that communication skill is an essential tool for producers, marketers and suppliers to draw the attention of potential buyers. The difference in languages and lack of basic education are the two basic obstacles for the rural marketers. Much of the success of tourism marketing depends on the ability to give warm welcome to the guest, to understand the clients’ (here visitor) demand and to provide right services at right time.

C. Insufficient Financial Support

Most of the rural tourism marketers come from the poor family background and not every time they are financially supported by the local banks or local Government bodies through loan facilities. Therefore, though these marketers have unique business ideas, most of the time because of insufficient fund, inadequate technical knowledge and skill they fail to start up businesses as per their desire.

D. Lack of Trained Human Resource

The success of rural tourism depends on the quality of hospitality service from welcome to see off the tourist as we all know the first impression is the last impression. But in rural areas, lack of trained human resource is a common issue that affects directly the tourism and hospitality industry badly. Moreover, the trained people from urban areas normally are not interested in going to rural areas to work due to lack of basic infrastructure facilities.

- Lack of access to markets. Rural residents may not know how to promote and distribute their product involving Manekpur weekly Haat as a local attraction.
- The local areas face from lack of accommodation facilities and services like F&B, like chikoo and mango agro products as retail businesses.
- Lack of adequate policies in support of rural tourism. Government has a key role to play in supporting rural tourism.

- The resources may not be finely managed for rural tourism development which has may lead to negative impacts on environment and culture.
- There may be lack of interest, awareness sand co-operation among people local representatives for participation in rural tourism. Lack of entrepreneurs also limits growth of tourism. In case the rural residents are not hospitable and friendly, it may not be a good experience for the tourists.
- Seasonality of demand also is a problem faced by rural tourism. Hence for many destinations it cannot be depended upon as a full time source of income generation.
- At times rural tourism creates pseudo employment scenario and cannot be considered a solution for employment generation unless jobs are created in real terms.

E. Issues with current development

Figure 12 Chart showing satisfaction and dissatisfaction rate of temple visitors

Figure 13 Chart showing facilities availed from Temple Authorities

VII. SWOT ANALYSIS OF KAMESHWAR MAHADEV MANDIR

A. Strength

- Kameshwar Mahadev mandir is rich in wealth of archaeological sites and Religious place
- Kameshwar Mahadev mandir has got good connectivity options via State Highways and railways.
- Good number of local and domestic tourists visiting this destination.
- Unique culture of the local people.
- Already existing tourism infrastructure.
- Rich natural/cultural resources and geographical diversity

B. Weakness

- lacks in wide varieties of accommodations facilities and adequate drinking water
- Facilities at various tourist spots. It does not have adequate public toilets and that are there, are in poor/unusable conditions.
- Poor street lights are the major concerns in places like Gadat to Kameshwar mahadev mandir road.
- Do not have sufficient accommodation facilities to attract large number of tourists.
- Lack of quality trained guides and the quality of the tourism information centres.
- Lack of coordination among local people.
- Low involvement of local people in tourism.

C. Opportunities

- For the purpose of investment in tourism sector, depending on the size of the project and its importance to the State's development, concessions would be provided either on the lease and its tenure or on the rate to be charged for Government land and on stamp duty and registration fee on And transaction for the Tourism Projects.
- Local or Domestic tourism has bloomed in India over the years.
- There is good opportunity to increase the reach of tourism by effectively using the social media space.
- Kameshwar mahadev mandir has potential opportunity to become a preferred tourist destination globally through its rich and diverse cultural heritage, abundant natural resources and biodiversity provides numerous tourist attractions.

D. Threats

- The emergence of the neighboring state as popular tourist destinations can hamper local tourism.
- Pollution by sewage, dumping of the wastes in lake.
- Tourists' dissatisfaction after visiting this place.
- Every trust has a limited shelf life. After a certain span of time, the trust becomes ineffective.

VIII. ACTION PLAN

A. Initiatives Envisaged

- Proposals on small and big developmental work from the relevant collector of six sacred religious places of Government namely Somnath, Ambaji, Girnar, Palitana, Dakor and Dwarka, approves them and undertaken them by sanctioning financial assistance. Accordingly, the money is allotted.
- Constitution of administrative committee related to the development of Yatradham by getting Government/ ULB approval.
- Getting approval of Government for the day-today management and rules of administrative matters of Yatradhams and implementation of the same.
- Any developmental work related to Yatradhams and religious places of state entrusted by the Government.
- Maintenance of holiness, cleanliness and beauty etc, at Yatradham.
Planning for making available various facilities for the pilgrims at Yatradhams.
- Acceptance of gifts, fund, donation etc, and integrated planning to use it for the development of Yatradhams.
- Undertaking various basic developmental works like water, sewerage, parab, road and garden in a planned manner at Yatradham.
Providing food and other requirements (including cash) to the pilgrious at the time of natural calamity.
- Acquisition of immovable properties in relation to the overall development at Yatradhams and modifications in the same.
- Publication of public important literature related to Yatradhams and observation on the use of it for the public.
- Consultation with the government, semi-government and voluntary organizations referring to the objectives of board in development of Yatradham and fulfillment of the same.
- Undertaking project for research on these Yatradhams and constitution of a committee in this reference if required.

Agreements with relevant authority, Municipal Corporation, local authority etc, in relation to the development of Yatradham.

- Organization of gramsabha, meetings, functions etc, related to development of Yatradham.
- Undertaking any development work for the aims of board and the agreement under the same.
- Publishing sufficient information on various activities of board for the public through newspaper. Exhibition at various places and publication of such literature in the form of books.
- Developing and providing financial support for infrastructure facilities such as civic amenities, accommodation and other tourism infrastructure;
- Prioritizing the development of wayside amenities along the major arterial highways of the State;
- Granting additional financial support for tourism development to special areas to be identified from time to time

B. Local Vision

Existing Tourism Unit taking up expansion of more than fifty percent of its existing capacities (e.g. Rooms/Rides/Tents, etc.) Only one expansion project (commencing commercial operations within the Policy Period) of an existing tourism unit will be eligible for assistance during the operative period of the Policy.

C. Mythological value enhancement

Tourism development can also be done by its cultural and religious value where organism of human society is involved due to Kameshwar mahadev temple.

D. Resource value enhancement

As the town is located in the fringe area – between rural and urban some landscaping elements can be initiated to demarcate the physical boundaries – giving a districts urban characteristics.

For examples: like Lake , Trees , shrubs , continuing along with the agriculture filed boundaries.

Giving proper boundaries like treating the shore line of lake water bodies, against erosion. The natural pathways can be retained by providing paver blocks. And avoiding hard landscaping. And promoting more of soft landscape which

allows water seepage to ground which in a way helping to increase and maintaining ground water table.

The resource conservation can be done by managing the land in proper way the dedicated agricultural land should be for the farming only it should not be converted into non- agricultural land as there is a threat of village expansion and the town is near the fringe of new city expanded limit. (GOVERNMENT BODY: NUDA)

Main idea is to enhance the “Natural Experience in a Rural Setting” and draw attention to uniqueness of rural setting.

The resource management:

1. Identifying the different types of birds, animals, fishes, butterflies etc.
2. Identifying the different types of trees, fruits, vegetation etc. Available in surrounding which can be protected as conservation policies.

E. Ecological Value Enhancement

- The lake and forest area can be conserved by adopting the various strategies for no development area, creating some barrier near the lakes to avoid pollution of water.
 - Organizing the various public awareness camps for the conservation of green area and for preserving the lake water by giving them knowledge about various alternatives.
 - And financial values can be preserved by maintaining the religious and cultural value by type of eco – tourism through the existing forest and natural features. To experiencing rural life style on weekends. This will improve income prospect without turning rural areas into urban areas which will in a way create another employment opportunity to people resending village other than agriculture and shrimp farming.
1. The development of water safety plans,
 2. The assessment of risk at all stages between catchment and consumer.

F. Socio-economic value enhancement

- So they can maintain this and generate economy by it’s by products and tourism development.
- Engaging in conservation can avail the area regularly for a fixed fee. Nature club’s activities, photography club’s

activities and school picnics can be done as guided tours which can enhance the socio- economic value of the site

- Understanding the economic conditions of the region, main sources of livelihood and income in the community assists in identifying causal factors that may lead to environmental pressure and degradation of resources.
- Economically the district relies heavily on the agricultural related activities. However, due to lack of market and dilapidated infrastructure no significant income is realized from activities.

G. Cultural value enhancement

Whole region having highly agricultural land. Conservation and maintain essential ecological process and life- support system in terms of soil regeneration and the recycling of nutrients. They should change crops on each land for above mentioned things.

H. Project benefit and impact assessment

By all this people of this small village can earn same economy that of any urban area so in next few years when this region is a part of gadat extended boundary. They won't attracted towards development and conserve their Rurban identity.

As the multiple sustainable developments of the village two main criteria which can be focused is main is tourism dimension, ecological dimension, economic dimension and political dimension.

Ecological Dimension :

As the lake which is almost 100 years old and also the lake during the seasons is full with lotus flowers and small fishes, due to the increase in village population the lake is being used for washing clothes, pujas during festival and other issues have polluted the lake which need to preserve and conserve for future.

Suggestions for preservation of lake

By providing separate washing areas for cloths, cattle's, bathing so that water body is not polluted wastewater drainage into septic tank recycling and for watering surrounding landscape.

Economic Dimension

As the temple complex is old structure and have its religious importance it attracts more tourism and the village depends on that economic as the proper structure is formed which will

increased the tourism and marketing will give good economy to the village people.

During the festival periods village people use to sell vegetable and other stalls to attract the tourist people which is the income for the local people there so to provide a proper market place will help the without destroying the temple complex.

Other main activity is the shrimp farming as the village is located on the edge of the coastal area one side of the area is not used for agriculture farming so shrimp farming is done which is the other main economic of the village so as number to people used to come for temple we can also increase the tourism for shrimp farming which will also help for economic and development of the village.

Suggestions for better economic development

By providing proper storage facilities and management of PDS (Public Distribution System) for related to shrimp farming will increase income.

Alternative Way of Earning

Most of the rural dwellers around this area are dependent on traditional agricultural activities to maintain their livelihood. In this connection, rural tourism can be a potential tool to reduce their over dependency on cultivation and it contributes to the overall economic development of an area that would otherwise be deprived.

Political Dimension

As the temple complex the major trustiest of the temple is from the nearby village named gadat as there are village which are involved and are creating the awareness for the temple due to which the road and other facilities of the village is being increased and also the nearby area have been developed for the weekend housed schemes which increase the tourism and also the growth and development of the village will increase and

Suggestions for better development of the village:

The village that is Amalsad which have major trusties and village Gadat which have main temple complex can come to gather as one village which will increase the development economic of village and also the preservation of the resource can be done in better ways as it would be in the hand of the trusties which will preserve the resource of the village

Inferences

Figure 17 Tourism's impact on rural economy

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